

Answers for *How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010*

General

Topic

What is the main research question of the project?

How population is affected by suicide rates?

Please give some keywords describing the research question.

- population
- suicide
- 1985-2010
-

Research field

Which research field(s) does this project belong to?

- Engineering Sciences / Production Technology
- Engineering Sciences / Computer Science

Which persons or institutions are responsible for the project coordination?

- TU-WIEN
- Mr.Tomasz Miska

Project schedule

When does the project start?

March 19, 2019

When does the project end?

April 22, 2019

Project coordination

Which persons or institutions are responsible for the project coordination?

- TU-WIEN
- Mr.Tomasz Miska

Other requirements I

Are there requirements regarding the data management from other parties (e.g. the scholarly/scientific community)?

Yes

Other requirements II

Which are these additional requirements regarding data management?

for more details go and visit: The World Bank (Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)) <https://www.worldbank.org/en/about/legal/terms-of-use-for-datasets> and Creative Commons CC Zero License (cc-zero) : <http://opendefinition.org/licenses/cc-zero/>

Content classification

What kind of dataset is it?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): Total population (in millions) by country, 1980 to 2010. Compiled by Energy Information Administration (EIA).

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: This compiled dataset pulled from four other datasets linked by time and place, and was built to find signals correlated to increased suicide rates among different cohorts globally, across the socio-economic spectrum.

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: This dataset is compiled from two different datasets: Population by Country (1980 - 2010) and Suicide Rate Overview 1985 to 2016.

Is the dataset being created or re-used?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): Re-used

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: Re-used

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: Created

If re-used, who created the dataset?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): The dataset was created and collected by Energy Information Administration (EIA).

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: 1- United Nations Development Program. (2018). Human development index (HDI). 2- World Bank. (2018). World development indicators: GDP (current US\$) by country:1985 to 2016. 3- [Szamil]. (2017). Suicide in the Twenty-First Century [dataset]. 4- World Health Organization. (2018). Suicide prevention.

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:

If re-used, under which address, PID or URL can the dataset be found?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): <https://catalog.data.gov/dataset/population-by-country-1980-2010>

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: <http://hdr.undp.org/en/indicators/137506> , <https://databank.worldbank.org/data/development-indicators#> , <https://www.kaggle.com/szamil/suicide-in-the-twenty-first-century/notebook> , https://www.who.int/mental_health/suicide-prevention/en/

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:

Which individuals, groups or institutions could be interested in re-using this dataset? What are possible scenarios?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): students , researchers, and research organizations.

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: students , researchers, and research organizations.

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: students , researchers, and research organizations.

Is the dataset reproducible in the sense that it could be created / collected anew in case it got lost?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): yes, with moderate, but reasonable effort

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: yes, with moderate, but reasonable effort

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: yes, with moderate, but reasonable effort

Technical classification

When does data collection or creation start?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): Aug. 29, 2017

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: Dec. 1, 2018

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: March 22, 2019

When does data collection or creation end?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): Oct. 9, 2017

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: Dec. 1, 2018

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: Dec. 14, 2018

When does data cleansing / data preparation start?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: March 23, 2019

When does data cleansing / data preparation end?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: March 24, 2019

When does data analysis start?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: March 21, 2019

When does data analysis end?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: March 21, 2019

What is the actual or expected size of the dataset?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): exact size: 61 KB

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: exact size: 396 KB

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: less than 1 GB

How much data is produced per year?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:

Which file formats are used?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): CSV (Comma-separated values)

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: CSV (Comma-separated values)

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: CSV (Comma-separated values)

Which tools, software, technologies or processes are used to generate or collect the data?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): not mentioned by the publisher: National Renewable Energy Laboratory

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: not mentioned by the publisher

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: python IDE , CSV file reader

Which software, processes or technologies are necessary to use the data?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): not mentioned by the publisher: National Renewable Energy Laboratory

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: not mentioned by the publisher

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:

Is documentation about relevant software needed to use the data?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): No

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: No

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: No

Are different versions of the dataset created?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): No

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: No

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: No

Which versioning strategy is applied for this dataset?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:

Which technology or tool is used for versioning?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:

Data usage

How / for what purpose will this dataset be used during the project?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): to make a correlation between this dataset and other dataset used in the project to show the desired results.

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: to make a correlation between this dataset and other dataset used in the project to show the desired results.

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: this dataset is the output results of other two datasets used in the project.

How often will this dataset be used?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): whenever needed to be used

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: whenever needed to be used.

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: whenever needed to be used.

To what extent will infrastructure resources be required (e.g. CPU hours, bandwidth, storage space... etc.).

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): Infrastructure resources of the usual workplace equipment are sufficient.

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: Infrastructure resources of the usual workplace equipment are sufficient.

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: Infrastructure resources of the usual workplace equipment are sufficient.

Are there actual or potential usage scenarios that could benefit from support by a data management or IT expert, or that even require such support?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): No

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: No

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: No

Where is the dataset stored during the project?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): on GitHub Repository also on a local storage.

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: on GitHub Repository also on local storage.

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: on Github Repository , and on local storage.

Under which URL can the dataset be accessed during the project?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): <https://github.com/samihabakri/datasetExercise>

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: <https://github.com/samihabakri/datasetExercise>

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: <https://github.com/samihabakri/datasetExercise>

Are there internal project guidelines for a consistent organisation of the data? If so, where they are documented?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): No

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: No

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: No

Is there a internal project guideline for naming the data? If so, please briefly outline the naming conventions and, if necessary, link to the documentation.

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): No

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: No

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: No

Who is allowed to access the dataset?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): according to the publisher National Renewable Energy Laboratory under the license of Creative Commons CCZero data is available for public for more details please visit: <http://opendefinition.org/licenses/cc-zero/>

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: according to the publisher under the license of World Bank Dataset Terms of Use, data is available for public for more details please visit: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/about/legal/terms-of-use-for-datasets>

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: for public usage.

How and how often will backups of the data be created?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:

Who is responsible for the backups?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):</>

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Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:

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How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:

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Which measures or provisions are in place to ensure data security (e.g. protection against unauthorized access, data recovery, transfer of sensitive data)?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): for more information please visit : <http://opendefinition.org/licenses/cc-zero/>

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: for more information please visit: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/about/legal/terms-of-use-for-datasets>

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:

Is this dataset interoperable, i.e. allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries etc.?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):

- The dataset is usable with available (open) software applications or software applications that are established and widely used in the respective community: Creative Commons CC Zero License (cc-zero)

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:

- The dataset is usable with available (open) software applications or software applications that are established and widely used in the respective community: World Bank Dataset Terms of Use

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:

- The dataset is usable with available (open) software applications or software applications that are established and widely used in the respective community: World Bank Dataset Terms of Use and Creative Commons CC Zero License (cc-zero)

Will this dataset be published or shared?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): Yes, externally for everyone

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: Yes, externally for everyone

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: Yes, externally for everyone

If no, please explain why not. Please differentiate between legal and contractual reasons and voluntary restrictions.

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:

If yes, under which terms of use or license will the dataset be published or shared?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):

- Public domain (CC0)

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:

- Public domain (CC0)

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:

- Public domain (CC0)

If there are any restrictions on the re-use of this dataset, please explain why.

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:

When will the data be published (if they are)?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): Aug. 29, 2017

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: Dec. 1, 2018

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: April 17, 2019

Will the data be collaboratively used?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): No

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: No

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: No

Which platform / tools is / are used for collaboratively working on data and publications?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:

How is the collaborative work on the same files organised?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:

Which measures of quality assurance are taken for this dataset?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): For this dataset i have no idea what kind of quality assurance measures they are following but There are multiple perspectives on both quality and its measurement that depend on the stakeholder's point of view, but the most important measures are: to be Measurable, Actionable, Trackable over time, Maintained and updated regularly and Tied to business goals.

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: For this dataset i have no idea what kind of quality assurance measures they are following but There are multiple perspectives on both quality and its measurement that depend on the stakeholder's point of view, but the most important measures are: to be Measurable, Actionable, Trackable over time, Maintained and updated regularly and Tied to business goals.

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: As stakeholder for this data the most important measures are: to be Measurable, Actionable, Trackable over time, Maintained and updated regularly, Tied to business goals.

Data integration

Is the integration between the re-used and newly created data ensured? If yes, by which means?

No.

Costs

What are the personnel costs for data management associated with the creation or acquisition of data in the project?

0.5 PM

What is the amount of non-personnel-costs for data management associated with the creation or acquisition of data in the project?

0 Euro

What are the personnel costs for data management associated with the the usage of data in the project?

0.5 PM

What is the amount of non-personnel-costs for data management associated with the usage of data in the project?

0 Euro

What are the personnel costs associated with data storage and data security in the project?

0.5 PM

What is the amount of non-personnel costs associated with the storage of the data sets during the project?

0 Euro

Metadata and referencing

Which information is necessary for other parties to understand the data (that is, to understand their collection or creation, analysis, and research results obtained on its basis) and to re-use it?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):</>

- Location
- Content
- Methodology
- Time
- Sources

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:</>

- Location
- Content
- Time
- Sources

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:</>

- Location
- Content
- Methodology
- Time
- Sources

Which standards, ontologies, classifications etc. are used to describe the data and context information?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):</>

- Discipline-specific standards, classifications etc. are used: Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:</>

- Discipline-specific standards, classifications etc. are used: Creative Commons CCZero

Which metadata are collected automatically?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): There is no metadata collected automatically.

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: Not mentioned by the dataset owner.

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: There isn't metadata collected automatically

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): Yes

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: Yes

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: Yes

Which metadata are collected semi-automatically?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): not mentioned by the dataset owner.

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: Not mentioned by the dataset owner.

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: N/A

Which metadata are collected manually?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): not mentioned by the dataset owner.

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: Not mentioned by the dataset owner.

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: all of the metadata.

Are metadata and context information being checked for correctness and completeness?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):</>

- Other

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:</>

- Other: Not mentioned by the dataset owner.

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:</>

- Other

Who is responsible for documenting the metadata and context information and for checking if they are correct and complete?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):</>

- no mentioned by the dataset owner.

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:</>

- Not mentioned by the dataset owner.

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:</>

- The dataset owner

Metadata costs

What are the personnel costs associated with the the creation of metadata and context information in the project?

0.5 PM

What is the amount of non-personnel-costs associated with the creation of metadata and context information in the project?

0 Euro

What is the structure of the data? How are the individual components of the dataset related to each other? How is the dataset related to other datasets used in the project?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): using CSV format in all files , data has to be related in order to be able to make a relation between other datasets, such as the date and country names in both datasets.

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: using CSV format in all files , data has to be related in order to be able to make a relation between other datasets, such as the date and country names in both datasets.

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: using CSV format in all files , data has to be related in order to be able to make a relation between other datasets, such as the date and country names in both datasets and the suicide number in order to be able to make a correlation between them on the figure.

Will persistent identifiers (PIDs) be used for this data set?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): Yes

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: Yes

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: Yes

Which system of persistent identifiers shall be used?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): Handle / DOI

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: Handle / DOI

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: Handle / DOI

Which (sub-) entities / sub units should be referenced using identifiers? Which of those identifiers should be persistent and citable?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:

Who is responsible for the maintenance of the PIDs and the object maintenance (i.e. who is responsible notifying the PID-Service about object relocation and the new address)?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):</>

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Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:</>

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How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:</>

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PIDs costs

What are the personnel costs associated with of persistent identifiers in the project?

0.5 PM

What is the amount of non-personnel-costs associated with persistent identifiers in the project?

0 Euro

Legal and ethics

General legal issues

Does the legal situation of different countries have to be considered?

No

Does this dataset contain personal data?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): No

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: No

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: No

Does this dataset contain sensitive data other than personal data?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): No

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: No

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: No

If yes, please describe the non-personal sensitive data used in the project.

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:

Does the funder have rules or recommendations for data management? If yes, please briefly outline them and refer to more detailed sources of information if necessary. Please also indicate, if the rules / guidelines are mandatory or optional.

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): not mentioned.

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: not mentioned

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: not mentioned

Official approval

Has the project been approved by a research ethics committee?

No, a review is not necessary, because: there is no personal data

Is a statutory approval / permit needed for the research?

No

If yes, which permit?

If yes, which is the responsible agency?

Is a data access committee needed to handle access requests to the published data of the project?

No

Intellectual property rights I

Does the project use and/or produce data that is protected by intellectual or industrial property rights?

No

Storage and long-term preservation

Selection

What are the criteria / rules for the selection of the data to be archived (after the end of the project)?

input , output data that were used to create the visualization.

Who selects the data to be archived?

- Researcher Samiha Albakri

Does this dataset have to preserved for the long-term?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): Yes

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: Yes

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: Yes

What are the reasons this dataset has to be preserved for the long-term?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):</>

- Re-use in subsequent projects or by others
- Documentation, because it is relevant to society
- Self-commitment

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:</>

- Used in a publication / proof of good scientific practice
- Re-use in subsequent projects or by others
- Self-commitment

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:

- Used in a publication / proof of good scientific practice
- Re-use in subsequent projects or by others
- Documentation, because it is relevant to society
- Self-commitment

How long will the data be stored?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): no limits.

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: no limits

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: no limits.

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable.

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): no limits.

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: no limits

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: no limits.

Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) be stored or archived after the end of the project?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010):

- Generic data center: Zenodo

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016:

- Generic data center: Zenodo

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010:

- Generic data center: Zenodo
- Other

Is the repository or data centre chosen certified (e.g. Data Seal of Approval, nestor Seal or ISO 16363)? (If the dataset is archived at several places, you may answer this question with yes, if this applies to at least one of these.)

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): Yes

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: Yes

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: Yes

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): No

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: No

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: No

Shall there be an embargo period before the data are made available?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): No, it's available all the time

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: No, it's available all the time.

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: No, it's available all the time.

How will the identity of the person accessing the data will be ascertained?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): by using individual user account authentication.

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: by using individual user account authentication.

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: by using individual user account authentication.

By when will the data be archived?

Population by Country (1980 - 2010): April 17, 2019

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016: April 17, 2019

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010: April 17, 2019

Long-term preservation costs

What are the personnel costs associated with long-term preservation for the project?

0.5 PM

How will the datamanagement costs of the project be covered?

There is no data management costs in this project.

What is the amount of non-personnel-costs regarding long-term preservation for the project?

0 Euro